

INTRODUCING PSYCHOLOGICAL LITERACY

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The term 'psychological literacy' was introduced over two decades ago by Alan Boneau. In his 1990 paper, Boneau identified 100 psychological terms and concepts 'of sufficient importance that they should be general knowledge within the psychological community, especially to students' (p.891) that would form 'a comprehensive and irreducible knowledge base for psychology' (p.900).

Since then, the central concepts he identified have become less central to the discipline and the notion of psychological literacy has changed. Although there is no single agreed definition of psychological literacy, McGovern *et al.* (2010) claim it constitutes 'being insightful and reflective about one's own and others' behaviour and mental processes' and having the ability to apply 'psychological principles to personal, social, and organizational issues in work, relationships and the broader community' (p.11). Accordingly, 'psychologically literate citizens' are defined as those students who develop as a result of their Psychology degree into 'critical scientific thinkers and ethical and socially responsible participants in their communities' (p.10). That is, they are 'global citizens' (Stevens & Gielen 2007) who are able to apply their subject knowledge and associated skills and attributes to problem solving and interacting with the everyday world around them.

In their comprehensive exploration of psychological literacy, Cranney, Botwood and Morris (2012) define psychological literacy as 'the general capacity to adaptively and intentionally apply psychology to meet personal, professional and societal needs' and global citizenship as 'the understanding of global interrelatedness, and the capacity to live, work and contribute positively as a member of global communities'.

They present key issues that have arisen in Australia as a result of national and international change in higher education (HE) in general and in Psychology education and training in particular. These same issues exist in the United Kingdom (UK): large numbers of Psychology graduates do not go on to further professional training in Psychology, and there is an increasingly recognized need for professionals and citizens with high levels of psychological literacy and global citizenship (Trapp *et al.* 2011). Embedding the concepts of psychological literacy and psychologically literate citizenship is gaining pace in Australia and the United States of America (USA), but progress in the UK has been slower.

Many of the suggestions in this guide develop ideas discussed at a meeting of the BPS, Association of Heads of Psychology Departments (AHPD), HEA and Experimental Psychology Society (EPS) in 2011 at which members agreed that the psychological community should 'promote the value of study and practice more vigorously and publicly' (Trapp *et al.* 2011, p.10). Moreover, Cranney and Dunn (2011) suggest the concepts of psychological literacy and the psychologically literate citizen need to be explicitly stated through wide dissemination and supported with exemplars. This guide aims to meet these needs for the academic psychological community in the UK by providing an understanding of the concepts and demonstrating how they can be applied within the Psychology undergraduate curriculum. It identifies the importance of psychological literacy and psychologically literate citizenship for students, graduates and academic staff.

The guide is organized as follows: first it highlights the ways in which psychological literacy is important for employability and global psychologically literate citizenship, and second, it provides examples within the Psychology curriculum where the development of psychological literacy can be demonstrated. Finally, we present the way forward: an argument for promoting psychological literacy in undergraduate Psychology courses.

The governments of the UK and higher education institutions (HEIs) themselves are concerned increasingly with the link between employability and course content (Business Innovation & Skills, BIS, 2011). This is highly salient for Psychology courses as only 15-20% of Psychology graduates pursue professional psychology careers (Quality Assurance Agency, QAA, 2010, p.2), meaning that the significant majority of students who complete a Psychology degree in the UK are employed outside professional or scientific psychology (Trapp *et al.* 2011). Consequently, it is imperative for educators to provide opportunities for Psychology students to apply their skills and knowledge to authentic problems in a range of contexts that demonstrate the broad application of psychological theory to real life and work situations. Following recent changes to accreditation criteria, the British Psychological Society (BPS 20121) advise including 'employability' within the undergraduate curriculum as good practice. The aim is to help Psychology graduates explore opportunities to apply evidence-based psychological thinking not only to the traditional chartered routes, but also in a multitude of careers. At the time of writing, a few undergraduate courses in the UK contain an element of work-based learning or a

placement (eg Huddersfield, Glasgow Caledonian University and Aston), and others are considering similar ideas.

The Higher Education Academy (HEA) recently produced a guide for Psychology departments to facilitate them in embedding employability into the Psychology curriculum (Reddy, Lantz & Hulme 2013), which provides case studies to illustrate such initiatives. Tomorrow's graduates will need to be flexible enough to perform jobs that do not yet exist (Trapp *et al.* 2011). For example, they will have to adapt to changing technology and keep up to date with information that has evolved, possibly unrecognizably, since they last engaged in formal study. Psychological literacy entails the desire and capability to become a lifelong learner; skills in information retrieval, critical evaluation and independent working are core attributes for learning across new contexts. Today's Psychology graduates should be well equipped to be tomorrow's leaders at all levels across any industry in which humans are involved. The National Committee of Inquiry into Higher Education (2009) argues that employers seek graduate employees who are numerate, able to write concisely and clearly, and communicate key findings effectively. Furthermore, in addition to the clear value of understanding quantitative methods, knowledge of qualitative methods (eg the design and analysis of focus group data and interview data) is critical to identifying existing issues in the workplace and to evaluating current practice. The Labor Force Survey for 2011-12 found that over that last decade, stress, depression or anxiety and musculoskeletal disorders accounted for the majority of days lost due to work-related ill health, 10.4 and 7.5 million days respectively (Health and Safety Executive 2012). At the same time a number of occupational psychologists and researchers working in this field have highlighted the importance of positive emotional wellbeing in the workplace and strategies to enhance wellbeing (Weinberg & Cooper 2007). Given these statistics, having the skills to propose and evaluate viable solutions to improve health at work is clearly a valuable asset that Psychology graduates should possess following research methods training.

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